

A Review of Digitalization Impacts of Microfinance Institutions in Growth of Indian Economy

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Abstract

Insufficiency suffering the poor with negative, unbearable and uncontrollable conditions, which limited them to exploiting services in the regular banking sector. The need to provide financial services to people in need of better quality of life through the organized sector has created microfinance in India. Microfinance institutions have come a long way in bringing about change, benefiting the poor and the marginalized by providing access to the capital. Also, the digitalisation of microfinance institutions has emerged as a new wave, and these agencies are working tirelessly to advance technology to enhance efficiency and effectiveness. This working paper identifies the evolution of the microfinance revolution in India as a powerful tool in the fight against poverty. If financial institutions fail to provide microfinance, the limit is very low. Question marks on the governance of microfinance institutions. A concerted effort is needed to contribute to the development of the new microfinance industry, while at the same time focusing on trade agreements between boundaries and sustainability.

This research paper outlines several aspects in which the government must play its role. This research paper also highlights the development of the microfinance industry, where the key issues are the diversification of access to capital, innovation in distribution, infrastructure and education, and the use of new technologies such as mobiles and smart government within the sole recognition authority of India. The research paper examines the evolution of microfinance and its associated factors and ideological position based on global recognition, a one-off proposal for both Microfinance institutions and clients.

Keywords: Digitalization Impacts, Microfinance Institutions, Financial Services.

Introduction

With the success of a small experiment conducted by Nobel Laureate Professor Muhammad Yunus, in the poverty-stricken and flood-ravaged Bangladeshi village of Jobra by providing a small amount as working capital to a few women, microfinance was born. Over the years, Microfinance has been proven to be one of the powerful tools for empowerment & most important & poverty alleviation as it provides the most tangible outcome within the shortest period. The Microfinance sector in India has traversed a long journey from micro-savings to microcredit and then to microenterprises and now entered the field of micro insurance, micro pension.

India is witnessing an increasing pace of development, mainly because of the digital revolution. A very strong development tool like microfinance is also undergoing a change in its operations and reach. The origin of Microfinance in India dates back to 1992 when the National Bank for Agriculture & Rural Development (NABARD) piloted the formal launch Self Help Group (SHG) Bank linkage program.

According to the census of India, 68.84% of the Indian population resides in rural areas. With nearly 60% of the population depended upon the agricultural sector there is wide underemployment. The result is abject poverty and low access to institutionalized credit. Financial inclusion, therefore, is a key tool for development. In India, the expansion of financial services in India started with the nationalization of all banks in the country during the late 1960s. This was strengthened with the establishing of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) in 1976. The microfinance sector in India expanded real motivation with the establishment of the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) in 1982. The Indian microfinance industry has been a strong enabler of financial inclusion of underserved and unbanked people in India. After digital India movement and the launch of Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) in 2014, financial inclusion is vigorously promoted to ensure delivery of banking services at an affordable cost to the vast sections of the unbanked group.

Over the last three decades, the sector has undergone dramatic changes and has been driven by many factors which include the transformation of microfinance providers, the demand-supply gap, regulatory framework, and expansion of funding sources. Several digital financial services programs have been launched across the globe, which has been successfully serving the population at the base of the pyramid. In India, several initiatives have been undertaken to build public infrastructure in the digital ecosystem space to leverage people in poverty alleviation.

Review of Literature

Shah and Patel (2017) Micro-finance is considered to be revolutionary because it aims at servicing the poor who were unfit to get financial services before. However, its growth is obstructed by several regulatory and working hurdles are threatening the smooth functioning of MFIs. The main hinders faced by MFIs in financing the poor were the high transaction cost & low productivity while reaching out to the indigent in terms of small credit at regular intervals.

Taruna and Yadav (2016) explained the need and challenges that were faced by the poor people in India and providing them financial help, in the way of microcredit to start their small businesses, so they can make income and provide for their families. The study explored some glaring issues, challenges and offers some suggestions to make microfinance more effective. Government, RBI and various MFIs faced various challenges and to overcome with these challenges and issues; some preventive measures were also taken by these financial bodies to provide benefits to the poor people and social class of the society. Based on need, issues and challenges related to microfinance, the study predicted the new agenda for the future.

Dey (2015) to have a sustainable life style along with saving and investment, microfinance allows the poor to get the loan that leads to financial independence and growth. The poor use these loans in a productive manner to create their businesses, assets of their own and get rid of poverty once and for all. Microfinance is becoming a significant buzzword in India. Outstanding progress has been made through the last two decades in inventing techniques to deliver financial services to the poor on a sustainable basis. These loans are aimed at empowering the impoverished people to start their businesses and to grow their money so that they can achieve long-term financial independence and develop sustainably. Economic growth, sustainable development and poverty alleviation can be achieved effectively with the help of microfinance. This paper also focused on the challenges and suggestive measures for growth of microfinance in the Indian context for sustainable development.

Pokhriyal, Rani and Uniyal (2014) examined the role of microfinance intervention in promoting women empowerment in rural India. To check the various schemes under which the microfinance tool is applied, and the progress of this program, the help of various data provided by the government and other institutions was included in this study. It was suggested that education facilities and family protection must be provided proa perly. Microfinance institutions should be strengthened, and their support to recourse poor women should also be expanded.

Nasir, S (2013) tries to outline the prevailing condition of the microfinance in India in the light of its emergence till now, and it aims to provide a cost-effective appliance for providing financial services to the poor. The study finding discovers the fundamental gap in the functioning of MFIs such as applies in credit delivery, lack of product diversification, customer coinciding and with practical suggestions to overcome the issues and challenges linked with microfinance in India.

Sarkar &Baishya (2012) suggest that women’s uses to credit have a role in improving the domestic decision-making capacity, workforce contribution rate and control over resources and even political and legal consciousness, thus opening/prospect for greater empowerment of women.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the uses of digital finance in microfinance institutions.
- To study the uses of digital channels in microfinance institutions
- To study the impacts of digitalization in microfinance institutions.
- To study the digital economy and understand how digitalization improves our economic growth.

Research Methodology

This is exploratory research, reviewing the literature and qualitative and descriptive study based majorly on the analysis of secondary data of Digital economy and Micro Finance inclusion in India. The research methodology will be done in two steps: the first step consists of a recent bibliographical review on digitalization impact of Microfinance institutions (MFIs) in Indian economic growth, which shows the results and future measures recommended in the microfinance sector. The second step, the data collection on the Indian MFIs through the secondary sources in books, journal, newspapers and MFIs reports.

Importance of MFIs Digitalization

Stay competitive: With the recent regulatory approval to (SFBs) Small Finance Banks and the increased push for priority sector lending and financial inclusion for commercial banks by RBI, competition is increasingly intense in the sector. Additionally, MFIs can provide microfinance plus add-on services such as imparting best business practices, by using digital methods, entrepreneurial skilling and financial literacy training more effectively.

Protect against external shocks: Digitalization and the use of technology to streamline processes will reduce reliance on cash at the nodes of disbursement and collections and serve to protect MFIs against external shocks such as demonetization as well as make them more agile and adaptable to swift market movements.

Cost and process effectiveness: The adoption of digital solutions allows MFIs to cut costs through a variety of channels such as quicker processing times for disbursal and loan approval reduced costs of reduced risk of cash, physical data storage and some insulation from external shocks such as demonetization. There are also intangible cost reductions, such as the reduction in risk associated with the use and transportation of cash.

Impact of Microfinance

In each country, there is progress over time, but its level and speed may not be enough to maintain a satisfactory quality of life for the least profitable. In such cases, the intervention is to accelerate the natural pace of development. Microfinance is an intervention that seeks to expedite this process by improving household income by providing timely and appropriate support for economic activities, and by sharing government and mainstream financial sector responsibilities. In India, microfinance is at a new-born stage with massive potential for growth. Although the sector has begun to grow, challenges must be met to make this growth effective and sustainable. Microfinance needs to be more efficient, more customized and more comprehensive. To increase activity in this sector, we must develop financial expertise in microfinance institutions and establish relationships in the debt and equity capital markets. Microfinance can help transform India into an engine of economic growth.

Impact of Digitalization

The positive impact of digital technology on the reach of microfinance. MFIs have opportunities to leverage markets where mobile services are widely used to improve on large innovative technology projects and delivery channels. MFIs have the opportunity to be more transparent, reduce fraud risks, provide secure options to clients and field officers and mitigate cash risk, as the sector has been traditionally cash-intensive. Digital Financial Inclusion improves operational efficiency, reduce costs, and provide regular alerts to clients without any additional cost. But this is not effective pan-India. There is still a need for interventions to make the beneficiaries digitally literate. While it is undeniable that micro finance has had a great impact on the lives of poor Indians and that it has been one of the major contributors to the goal of poverty eradication.

Microfinance and Digitalization

While India is on the top list of first recipients of microfinance commercial financing, there are millions of people who are financially excluded. According to the World Bank, two billion people in the world lack access to financial services. Digitalisation has facilitated microfinance institutions to reach customers efficiently and conveniently. With the mobile users base increasing rapidly in India, channels such as Mobile devices which help in better tracking of transactions on a real-time basis. The reach of Microfinance in India was confined because of non-availability of a tool for mass reach. People who knew about microfinance could only take advantage of it, and a large portion remained untouched. With India, which is home to an unbanked population of around 47 per cent, technology can play a crucial role in driving financial inclusion of the underbanked as well as the un-banked population in the country.

Before Digitalization, microfinance was a means of financial inclusion, which included a very personal approach to the clients. On the one hand, the personal approach method to each client facilitated the direct connection of information about microfinance it restricted the outreach of knowledge. Digital technology has increased the scope of micro finance reach. Beneficiaries, equipped with mobile phones and regions connected with the internet, have made this possible. A woman in rural parts of the country is now better exposed to microfinance because of digital technology to leverage the micro-finance service due to lack of awareness. MFI's have opportunities to leverage markets where mobile services are widely used to improve on large innovative technology projects and delivery channels. MFIs have the opportunity to be more transparent, reduce fraud risks, provide secure options to clients and field officers and mitigate cash risk, as the sector has been traditionally cash-intensive. Digital Financial Inclusion improves operational efficiency, reduce costs, and provide regular alerts to clients without any additional cost. But this

is not effective pan-India. There is still a need for interventions to make the beneficiaries digitally literate.

Uses of Digital Finance in Microfinance Institutions

Microfinance institutions have played an essential role in financial inclusion, and they have understood that the use of new technologies enables them to strengthen their ability to reach populations that are unable to serve due to their geographical distance or economic situation.

The adoption of, therefore, digital tools, represents a critical opportunity for MFIs, in particular to:

- Expand their customer base by geographically expanding their activities and reaching new, low-income customer segments with cheaper services;
- Respond positively to the growing demand from your clients who can use their services after business hours and on weekends, which reduces travel time and meeting agent costs.
- Modernize certain costs and procedures of the organization;
- Expand your product range;
- Reduce the price of services offered;
- Promote the digital culture of their customers as a means to increase their independence.
- However, for many MFIs, the acceptance of digital financing instruments is not apparent due to many constraints:
 - The complexity of choosing and implementing the technologies available;
 - Economic availability and skills required to create and manage a mobile money system;
 - The scale to be achieved to justify the investment required; - the need for a strong banking IT infrastructure;
- Develop a clear strategy for using digital financial services.

To do this, they need to mobilize skills that most of them do not have, especially small and medium-sized microfinance institutions, which have fewer financial resources and are less able to take the risks that such a major change entails.

Uses of Digital Channels in Microfinance Institutions

Digitalization has facilitated microfinance institutions to reach customers more efficiently and conveniently at a lower cost. Varied innovative technologies that are leveraged by microfinance institutions are:

Personal Digital Assistant (PDAs): PDA as used by SKS microfinance for their operations is a portable computer like platform running software programs to standardize lending methodologies and assist in the collection of information. Software leads to time reduction by conducting loan scrutinization and disbursement of funds.

Management Information System (MIS): Automation due to the development of computers and software applications like MIS has transformed the way MFIs operate. Information is made readily accessible by MIS. It facilitates loan officers to track clients’ repayment schedules and balances and monitors progress toward attainment of operational objectives.

Mobile Device: India’s mobile banking subscriber base crossed one billion landmarks in January 2016. The mobile revolution has transformed the way financial services are provided. Several MFIs have made a successful foray into mobile technology for their operations through better tracking of transactions on a real-time basis, digitization of huge physical records, bringing higher levels of transparency in operations, time-saving & process efficiency and greater scalability.

Biometrics: With the evolvement of technology, biometric micro ATMs integrated with a biometric modality for authentication are contributing to the development of micro finance. Launch

of biometric micro ATM device “Aadhar Enabled Payment System” (AEPS) in 2012 by Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) has enabled beneficiaries with Aadhar to withdraw money near their doors through the core banking system. Micro ATM is connected to banks across the country. Biometric identity authentication is a must before performing transactions like withdrawing or putting money into their bank accounts. It enables MFIs to conduct secure transactions remotely besides eliminating the presence of staff members during authentication.

Indian Economy After Digitalization of MFIs

Keeping in view Government of India’s mission for creating digital India, NABARD launched a pilot project “E-Shakti” for the digitization of SHGs on 13 November 2014. E-Shakti enables maintenance of records of SHGs in electronic form and creation of MIS. Digitization of SHGs ensures access of members to a wide range of financial services. It concentrates on integrating SHG members with national financial inclusion and bringing persons under the umbrella of Aadhar. Moreover, it facilitates banks in extending the financial facility to SHGs by assessing their financial health.

Digital India, which was launched by the government in 2015, is a radical move, primarily to ensure that government services improve the online infrastructure and increase Internet connectivity, in an electronic form, for citizens to provide without interruption. India has a mobile subscriber base of 1150.45 million, which includes 489 million rural subscribers (TRAI, 2017) which indeed is the second-largest telephonic subscriber’s base in the world by number. It is evident that the government, towards digital empowerment of the people, has taken significant steps. One of the direct gainers of this initiative is the financial sector, wherein our country’s goal is to complete financial inclusion.

Technology and innovation have become key drivers of economic growth. In the recent past, technology has undoubtedly triggered economic growth, impacting significantly microfinance sector too. According to the World Bank, 2 billion people in the world today lack access to financial services. Digitization is profoundly changing the way financial services are being delivered by MFIs in India. A convergence of digital platform in financial inclusion benefits MFIs and clients alike. Automation of transactions due to digitization enables MFIs to enhance capital, the flow of information and makes it convenient to organize and scrutinize data. It has opened various opportunities by reducing the use of cash in operations resulting in significant cost savings and has also lead to an increase in outreach in a cost-effective manner. The database is easily searchable through internet by maintaining digitized information on the web. Furthermore, loan applications with a client in a remote village are now processed using a handheld device, eliminating the need for paper loan applications. Simultaneously clients are also benefitted by faster turnaround time of loan processing & approval, safe and secure way of repayment of loans through mobile wallets.

Conclusion

Microfinance institutions can leverage technology to speed up the flow of information, capital, and automate transactions, control and analyse data. It will also improve customer experience; reduce transaction costs, increase efficiency and customer outreach for them. The convergence of digital platform in financial inclusion will be beneficial to MFIs and clients alike. Digitalisation is the way ahead. To reach the last unbanked segment of the economy and for poverty alleviation of the economy, Digitisation of Microfinance is the most convenient and affordable way.

An outreach of MFIs due to digitization has undoubtedly increased in terms of its operations, clients and loan disbursement, but it has not been able to capture giant market share. Moreover, utilization of funds is more for non-productive and consumption activities. The government needs

to play a proactive role by ensuring the provision of funds for productive and developmental activities to fully utilize gains of digitalization. This goes without saying that the benefits churned will be manifold with high growth prospects, reduced operational costs, the scope of catering to more enormous masses with agility and speed. Some of the MFIs have gone a step ahead and passed on the part of the benefits to the members by lowering the interest rates. Technology will play a crucial role in bringing about financial Inclusion, and it is a great time to watch out for some really interesting and intriguing interventions.

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